

Deliverable D4.2

Common analysis environment

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1. Executive Summary

With the goal of providing a common environment to analyse, integrate and visualise COVID-19 related data, the Galaxy platform and its surrounding ecosystem were chosen as a scalable and expandable framework. In combination, the services of the ecosystem provide European researchers with a single environment to analyse multiple data types. The Galaxy Europe server¹ serves as an entrypoint for the environment, with WorkflowHub² also enhancing the findability of workflows. Within BY-COVID, we worked on several aspects to maximise its value as the common analysis environment for infectious disease-related data. Efforts were focused on designs and developments that could be readily integrated into the ecosystem, be reusable in the response to other infectious diseases, and that could connect and expand existing infrastructure.

For end-users, the added capabilities were made available for direct use in the Galaxy Europe server³. For infrastructure providers, enhancements were made available in the multiple related repositories and services^{4,5}. For general capacity building, training and dissemination material has been made available through existing⁶ and new resources⁷.

Developments that have been taking place within BY-COVID include:

- Addition of new analysis tools for infectious disease data and updates to existing ones
- Development of complete analysis workflows based on these and existing tools, and updates and improvements to existing workflows, which together enable the analysis of a diverse set of SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious disease data
- Addition of workflows directly related to the use cases in WP5

¹ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

² <https://workflowhub.eu/>

³ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

⁴ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy>

⁵ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

⁶ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

⁷ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/covid19-galaxy>

- Creation of public training materials demonstrating and explaining the analysis workflows, including interactions with WP6
- Work ensuring interoperability of the analysis environment with the COVID-19 Data Portal and MINERVA, with direct collaboration with WP6 and indirect collaboration with work conducted in WP1 and WP3
- Implementation of support for research object exchange standards (RO-Crate profiles) within the analysis environment with WP4
- Documentation of BY-COVID-related aspects of the analysis environment and its usage within BY-COVID through the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk) with WP4

The approach taken serves as an example on how to mobilise, repurpose, and expand existing compute and analysis infrastructures for infectious diseases research, surveillance, and rapid response to an outbreak.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	Yes
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes

<p>Objective 2</p> <p>Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres</p>	<p>1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.</p>	No
	<p>2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.</p>	Yes
	<p>4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.</p>	No
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p>	No
	<p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p>	No

<p>preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 5 Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
	<p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	<p>Yes</p>

3. Methods

With the goal of providing a common environment to analyse, integrate and visualise COVID-19 related data, efforts were made to build upon and connect existing initiatives and infrastructure. This strategy provided several advantages.

- The work could rely on already trained and knowledgeable infrastructure and service providers to more readily develop and integrate the tools and strategies to each of the common environment modules. The included, but were not limited to, the Galaxy Project, the European Galaxy server and associated compute power, the Galaxy Training Network, the WorkflowHub, the RO-Crate community, and domain experts that provided tools and workflows.
- The project made use of existing ways of working and development frameworks for each service, mitigating the management overhead of such a large initiative.
- The choice of expanding infrastructures and tools that were already in use contributed to the uptake of the solutions and to the longer term sustainability of the project's outputs.
- The approach further stimulates adoption and utilisation by leveraging the existing communities of the different adopted services.

In short, existing users could make direct use of new capabilities, while new users were onboarded onto an already thriving community. Moreover, many of the developments were implemented to allow their use in the context of other infectious diseases and monitoring, and even in general research. This allows the common analysis environment to remain of strategic importance between responses, and stay ready for recruitment and usage when a quick response to a new outbreak becomes necessary.

The common analysis environment was focused on the Galaxy platform and associated ecosystem. The Galaxy Project provides a powerful and versatile framework for data analysis in the life sciences and beyond, which gets leveraged in several ongoing EU initiatives and EOSC projects. The European Galaxy server⁸ and other public Galaxy servers⁹ use Galaxy to provide free and open-access platforms that enable data analysis on publicly funded compute-infrastructure, and the sharing of analysis results and workflows.

To achieve an interoperable and sustainable output, the work included interactions with several initiatives and groups, with a view of building upon existing efforts and enabling the necessary connections. This included work with the main development groups of the Galaxy Project¹⁰ itself, and associated groups, such as the Intergalactic Utilities Commission (IUC)¹¹ and Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC)¹² that provide oversight on tools and workflows respectively.

The project also contributed to and made use of the extensive training and dissemination capabilities of the Galaxy Training Network¹³ (GTN). The GTN offers researchers a free, open repository of online training materials for the Galaxy platform, emphasising hands-on

⁸ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

⁹ <https://galaxyproject.org/use/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy>

¹¹ <https://galaxyproject.org/iuc/>

¹² <https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc>

¹³ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

training designed to be directly applicable for learners. Work also included making use of outputs from other tasks in the project, such as implementing provenance definitions described in deliverable 4.3¹⁴, including the adoption of the developed RO-Crate profiles (see Section 4.5 for details). RO-Crates are an implementation of the Research Object concept. These are digital entities designed to improve the reuse and reproducibility of research by bundling together all relevant resources like data, code, and other materials in a shareable, machine actionable, and citable format.

To strengthen the interoperability of the analysis environment and the COVID-19 Data Portal, requirements and standards were exchanged with tasks of WP1 and WP3. Further grounding the efforts on real-world scenarios, use cases represented in WP5 were used as a source of workflows. To ensure dissemination in multiple levels, the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTK¹⁵, WP4) was used to expose documentation and examples. For further dissemination, training materials and events were developed with WP6.

Importantly, all enhancements produced as part of BY-COVID were contributed back to the Galaxy project's upstream repositories to ensure that these developments remain publicly available and are maintainable in the long term. All enhancements were also made available on Galaxy Europe as the flagship instance of the common analysis environment within BY-COVID.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Analysis tools

To make an analysis tool available in Galaxy it needs to be “wrapped”: the inputs, outputs and parameters of the tool need to be described. Galaxy uses the app store-like concept of toolsheds for publishing and distributing analysis tools wrapped for the platform, which allows administrators of individual Galaxy servers to install tools from trusted sources via a standardised interface. Tool authors can upload their work to toolsheds directly, or they can contribute their work via dedicated tool development repositories that provide code review, code quality checks and automated toolshed uploads.

Within the project, analysis tools relevant for infectious disease data were contributed via the development repository maintained by the IUC¹⁶, the Galaxy tools commission, which ensures a high-quality reviewing process. In a few exceptional cases we updated existing tools maintained in other repositories. All tools, once uploaded to the Galaxy project's main toolshed, were also made available via the European Galaxy server.

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/10927253>

¹⁵ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

¹⁶ <https://galaxyproject.org/iuc/>

Tools made newly available in the analysis environment or updated within the context of BY-COVID include:

- pangolin¹⁷ and nextclade¹⁸, the two most important tools for SARS-CoV-2 lineage assignment
- the ivar¹⁹ suite of tools for handling viral sequencing data obtained from tiled-amplicon sequencing
- varVAMP²⁰, a tool for designing tiled-amplicon and other PCR primer schemes
- MAFFT²¹, a popular tool for multiple sequence alignment
- lofreq²², a variant caller particularly useful for determining accurate allele frequencies from Illumina sequencing data
- Medaka²³ and Clair3²⁴, variant calling tools for Oxford Nanopore sequencing data
- SnpEff²⁵, for annotating the effect of genomic mutations
- VAPOR²⁶, a tool useful for determining subtypes of influenza samples
- freyja²⁷, lineagespot²⁸ and cojac²⁹, three tools for detecting SARS-CoV-2 lineages in waste-water sequencing data
- snipit³⁰ and other plotting tools for mutation profiles of SARS-CoV-2 and other viral samples

As part of this work, we also contributed a few bug fixes or smaller enhancements to the analysis tools themselves, in the upstream projects (pangolin, ivar, varVAMP, lineagespot, snipit).

4.2 Workflows

At its core, Galaxy has a workflow engine system that enables chaining of individual analysis tools into complex analysis workflows. Within BY-COVID, several such analysis workflows were created and mostly published via the Galaxy workflow commission (IWC³¹). In addition, workflows contributed to the IWC development repository are registered automatically at the WorkflowHub, making further use of the developed RO-Crate profiles (see Section 4.5 for details).

¹⁷ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=aaec941c4dfce850

¹⁸ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=67dbe502e3cad107

¹⁹ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=88b9d730de6633b9

²⁰ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=87c38961ae2926c2

²¹ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=5f987efbbb0e1901

²² https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=6949014feef6f2d5

²³ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=69a55bb1d512f519

²⁴ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=af46d3e473c0e7f2

²⁵ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=93a5efea7e957b53

²⁶ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=b788ce9cc54bd4bc

²⁷ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=390e9a437996278e

²⁸ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=374a889f1898b8b6

²⁹ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=86673806f86e7e7a

³⁰ https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repository/view_repository?id=f3182b2bfea6b59b

³¹ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc>

Workflows created and/or updated within the context of BY-COVID include:

Viral genomics workflows:

- A workflow collection for SARS-CoV-2 monitoring³² - workflows for the identification, annotation, reporting of mutations and viral consensus genome construction from SARS-CoV-2 sequencing data obtained through different sequencing techniques (Illumina paired-end or single-end, or Oxford Nanopore sequencing); 6 workflows overall. Within the ACTIV-TRACE programme led by the NCBI, these workflows were compared to similar pipelines developed by international partners from the public and private sector. This comparison resulted in some standardisation of the tool set being used in these workflows, in elimination of subtle errors and inconsistencies in the workflows and their underlying tools, and in general recommendations for reproducible and consistent SARS-CoV-2 variant detection.
- Two workflows for the analysis of tiled-amplicon and whole-genome sequencing data from pox virus samples^{33,34} - the workflows that can be used to analyse monkeypox samples, but also other pox virus samples like Capripox samples of major relevance in veterinary disease surveillance.
- an additional workflow for analysing sequencing data from Avian and seasonal influenza samples has been developed and is currently getting prepared for submission to the IWC repository³⁵
- an additional workflow for analysing wastewater sequencing data is currently under review at the IWC³⁶
- Workflows developed in collaboration with use cases in WP5, including a MINERVA integration, connecting Galaxy datasets to the MINERVA³⁷ Platform for visualisation of gene regulation patterns in humans infected with SARS-CoV-2³⁸:
 - The mRNA-Seq BY-COVID Pipeline: Counts workflow³⁹ - a workflow for generating genomic feature counts from RNA-sequencing data of SARS-CoV-2 patients and healthy controls.
 - The mRNA-Seq BY-COVID Pipeline: Analysis workflow⁴⁰ - a workflow building on the above workflow, for differential expression analysis, annotation and preparation of results for visualisation on the MINERVA platform's COVID-19 Disease Map.

³² <https://workflowhub.eu/collections/2>

³³ <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/439>

³⁴ <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/353>

³⁵ <https://usegalaxy.eu/published/workflow?id=4fdbf53ba08ca927>

³⁶ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc/pull/191>

³⁷ <https://minerva.pages.uni.lu/doc/>

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202403.1211.v1>

³⁹ <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/688>

⁴⁰ <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/689>

4.3 Training Materials

The Galaxy Training Network (GTN) is the standard for publishing Galaxy-related training materials. We contributed new tutorials to the GTN, which explain how specific analyses of infectious disease data can be performed within the analysis environment. More details can be found on the dedicated BY-COVID GTN page:

<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/hall-of-fame/by-covid/>

Training materials produced in the context of BY-COVID include:

- GTN:T00316⁴¹ - a tutorial detailing a complete analysis flow from sequencing data obtained from the COVID-19 Data Portal through mutation calling and viral consensus genome construction to SARS-CoV-2 lineage/clade assignment with pangolin and/or nextclade
- GTN:T00236⁴² - a tutorial showing how to remove traces of human genomic data from sequenced SARS-CoV-2 data
- GTN:T00347⁴³ - a tutorial on pox virus genome analysis from tiled-amplicon sequencing data
- GTN:T00308⁴⁴ - a tutorial on Avian influenza genome analysis from per-segment sequencing data
- GTN:T00437⁴⁵ a tutorial detailing contrast analysis of transcriptome data from COVID-19 patients and healthy controls showcasing also visualisation of results on the MINERVA Platform COVID-19 Disease Map

Several platform improvements to the GTN were also developed, including:

- Previews of workflows can now be embedded within tutorials, enabling authors of training materials to describe and discuss in more concrete terms what the workflow will do.
- The link between the GTN, WorkflowHub, and Galaxy has been improved and simplified: tutorial authors can embed a button in their tutorials which enables learners to launch a workflow in 2 clicks.

4.4 Interoperability with the COVID-19 Data Portal

We ensured bi-directional interoperability between the analysis environment and the COVID-19 Data Portal.

⁴¹ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00316>

⁴² <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00236>

⁴³ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00347>

⁴⁴ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00308>

⁴⁵ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00437>

Downloading data from the COVID-19 Data Portal is an integral part of the genome surveillance solution established in the analysis environment and described in a dedicated IDTk showcase (see Section 4.6 for details).

For uploading data from the analysis environment to the COVID-19 Data Portal, a dedicated upload tool was developed and contributed to the IUC repository following the same methodology as described for the analysis tools above. Within BY-COVID this tool received regular updates to keep up with specifications of the COVID-19 Data Portal.

In addition, slides (GTN:S00064⁴⁶) and a tutorial (GTN:T00159⁴⁷) were developed for the GTN to explain the details of using the tool and guide users through the upload process. A IDTk showcase was also created (see below).

4.5 Support for research object exchange standards

RO-Crate has emerged as a standard for research object exchange across several European initiatives including BY-COVID. The details of the standard and of the development work carried out within BY-COVID are described in the separate deliverable D4.3. On the analysis environment side, functionality was implemented for RO-Crate exports of workflow runs (as Workflow Run RO-Crates, WRROCs⁴⁸) and analysis results. For the former, a tutorial (GTN:T00340⁴⁹) was developed that explains the details from the user perspective.

Beyond enabling analyses that are better compliant with the FAIR principles and the envisioned EOSC Interoperability Framework⁵⁰, the adoption of RO-Crate as exchange format facilitated registration of workflows in WorkflowHub⁵¹, for the analysis environment as a whole. The former being a registry for computational workflows that acts as a facilitator for sharing of workflows. Moreover, RO-Crate's use of established web standards like schema.org enhances the interoperability of data within EOSC. This supports various projects, including EOSC-Life and other Horizon Europe initiatives, by providing a common metadata overlay that facilitates data sharing and integration across different repositories. The use of RO-Crate to collect crucial analysis parameters on the use of a workflow is thus an important step to increase trustworthiness of analysis results.

⁴⁶ <https://gxy.io/GTN:S00064>

⁴⁷ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00159>

⁴⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/>

⁴⁹ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00340>

⁵⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021,

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

⁵¹ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

4.6 Documentation via the Infectious Diseases Toolkit

A showcase page on “An automated SARS-CoV-2 genome surveillance system built around Galaxy”⁵² was created on the IDTk platform explaining how the analysis environment can be used for automated analysis of new data as it appears on the COVID-19 data portal. Two additional showcases were also added. The “SARS-CoV-2 sequencing in Estonia 2021-2022”⁵³ details how the analysis environment was used to power a national SARS-CoV-2 genome surveillance effort. The showcase on “Using the ENA data submission toolbox for SARS-CoV-2 data”⁵⁴ details the use of the platform for the processing and submission of viral data to the relevant data repository, enabling further use of the pathogen data.

The IDTk is a knowledge exchange platform aiming to provide general guidelines, signpost national resources, and showcase efforts and solutions in handling infectious diseases data. It will be described in more detail in the BY-COVID deliverable 4.1.

5. Results

The initial version of the SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequencing data analysis using the Galaxy environment was published in Maier et al. 2021⁵⁵ and was used to understand the origin of the omicron lineage of SARS-CoV-2⁵⁶. Insights from the NCBI-led ACTIV-TRACE project resulted in a publication further exploring standardisation of analysis⁵⁷.

As mentioned above, the analysis environment has powered the national SARS-CoV-2 genome surveillance effort of Estonia, but has also seen use by others inside and outside BY-COVID, for example in the work of Jaki et al. 2023⁵⁸, Vukovikj et al. 2023⁵⁹, and Izquierdo-Lara et al. 2023⁶⁰.

The analysis environment and its use in infectious disease data analysis was featured prominently in the one-health module of a global Galaxy training week in Spring 2023⁶¹, in two Regional Training Courses on next-generation sequencing for animal virus monitoring organised by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and supported by ELIXIR

⁵² <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/covid19-galaxy>

⁵³ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/korogenoest>

⁵⁴ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/ena-data-submission-toolbox>

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-021-01069-1>

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msac061>

⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.3390/v16030430>

⁵⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-37591-w>

⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3389/fviro.2022.1064882>

⁶⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162209>

⁶¹ <https://gallantries.github.io/video-library/modules/one-health>

Slovenia^{62,63}, and in a talk at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2023. The partnership with the IAEA is still on-going and will result in new adaptations of the initial workflow for other infectious diseases.

6. Discussion

The BY-COVID project brings together diverse communities that each contribute relevant data to improve our understanding of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and how it affects us. To bring this data together, a common analysis environment is needed that can handle the diverse types of data. The project adopted Galaxy and made relevant tools, workflows, data and training materials available, enabling it to serve as such a common analysis environment for infectious diseases. From a maintainability standpoint, the project's improvements have been integrated into the Galaxy's main repositories. This ensures continuation of work and their public accessibility beyond the project's timeline. From the standpoint of the research community, the developments are also directly available for use on Galaxy Europe⁶⁴.

Enabling access to input data as well as publishing the results in a FAIR way is essential for an effective common analysis environment. The work done has ensured interoperability between the analysis environment and the COVID-19 Data Portal. This has been achieved by developing a dedicated upload tool and creating and disseminating materials to guide users through the upload process. The project has also implemented functionality for RO-Crate exports of workflow runs and analysis results, enabling traceability of the entire analysis and thus contributing to the overall building of trust in the obtained results.

One of the challenges in the beginning of the pandemic was the findability of the efforts done across Europe. Therefore the work done has been described in showcase pages on the IDTK platform, e.g. explaining how the analysis environment can be used for automated analysis of new data as it appears on the COVID-19 data portal, its use in a national surveillance effort, and its use in helping making critical data accessible.

One of the key aspects contributing to successful developments in the efforts described here was the leveraging of the existing infrastructures and initiatives. While connecting the different working groups may pose an initial challenge, the scaffolding of the BY-COVID project allowed for interactions and exchanges between the stakeholders so as to promote the necessary connections between different ways of working and processes. These translated into the uptake of new and existing technologies, while making computational power, workflows, and data more readily available to the research community.

⁶² <https://elixir.mf.uni-lj.si/enrol/index.php?id=99>

⁶³ <https://elixir.mf.uni-lj.si/enrol/index.php?id=103>

⁶⁴ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

7. Conclusions

With the work described here, in the BY-COVID project we implemented new tools, workflows, and expanded the use of standards, thus effectively establishing a common analysis environment, based on the Galaxy Project. This allowed us to provide a robust, versatile, and interoperable analysis environment for diverse infectious disease-related data. The project's enhancements have been contributed back using the standard methodologies of the community. This ensures that it can be maintained in the future and therefore remain available in the long term. Through the adoption of technologies supported e.g. ELIXIR to capture provenance (RO-Crate) and WorkflowHub to publish workflows, the developments made during the project will continue to benefit the scientific community in the long term.

Overall, BY-COVID has demonstrated the effectiveness of using, connecting and expanding existing infrastructures to meet the urgent needs of infectious disease research and surveillance. The science it enabled has contributed to our understanding and management of infectious diseases.

8. Next steps

As part of the design in defining a common analysis environment for BY-COVID, the efforts described here can be followed up in several ways. The common analysis environment continues to be available after the conclusion of BY-COVID. This includes availability of tools and workflows through Galaxy Europe⁶⁵, the Galaxy network, and WorkflowHub, allowing for the continuation of COVID related research and surveillance efforts. This is an important aspect for the collaboration with the joint FAO/IAEA Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory Network (VETLAB), with whom we are currently working on newly adopted workflows for several other infectious diseases. Further developments to the core components and infrastructure of the common analysis environment, including developments that are added to the Galaxy roadmap, are part of new projects. As an example, EuroScienceGateway⁶⁶ includes tasks to expand the use of RO-Crates. It also includes developments for a more flexible system to make use of external storage and compute power. These will enable users and institutions to bring their own resources and will further open capabilities for federated data analysis while maintaining a common environment and its interoperable qualities. The mobilisation of a common analysis environment in response to an outbreak can lead to a rapid increase in the demand for compute power, making efficient resource usage an important parameter. Further aspects

⁶⁵ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

⁶⁶ <https://eurosciencegateway.eu/>

on increasing the efficiency of usage of compute resources and reducing their environmental impact is also part of subsequent projects, including ELIXIR-STEERS⁶⁷.

9. Impact

The surveillance system described in IDTK⁶⁸ has aided in the analysis of at least half-a-million samples. In addition, the sequencing initiatives in Estonia making use of the systems described here had, up until March 2023, led to the submission of more than 23000 viral sequences to the ENA repository⁶⁹.

Further underscoring the reusability of the solutions described here, the material and the server are used further beyond BY-COVID, for example in a course on the analysis of Mycobacterium tuberculosis related data⁷⁰ organised by Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute⁷¹, SANBI/UWC⁷², PANGenS⁷³ and others.

Moreover, the original publication by Maier et al. 2021 has, at the time of writing, 21 citing publications in Google Scholar⁷⁴. Further highlighting the international impact of the actions described here, these publications include the work of Wertheim and Wang et. al 2022⁷⁵ investigating variants of interest in the US, and of Zhou et al. 2022⁷⁶, in which research groups in China investigate lineage composition in viral samples.

⁶⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers>

⁶⁸ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/covid19-galaxy>

⁶⁹ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/korogenoest>

⁷⁰ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/events/2024-06-10-mtb-ngs.html>

⁷¹ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/hall-of-fame/swiss-tph/>

⁷² <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/hall-of-fame/sanbi/>

⁷³ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/hall-of-fame/pangens/>

⁷⁴ https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cites=987656929286200935&as_sdt=2005&scioldt=0,5

⁷⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31247-x>

⁷⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2022.07.042>